

A MODERN APPROACH TO THE EXAMINATION OF LIVER FIBROSIS USING ULTRASOUND

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Abstract: Liver fibrosis is a pathological condition characterized by the excessive accumulation of extracellular matrix proteins due to chronic liver injury. Early detection and accurate staging of liver fibrosis are crucial for preventing progression to cirrhosis and liver failure. Traditionally, liver biopsy has been the gold standard for diagnosing liver fibrosis, but it is invasive and carries risks. In recent years, non-invasive ultrasound-based techniques, such as transient elastography (FibroScan) and shear wave elastography (SWE), have emerged as valuable alternatives to biopsy. These methods are safe, cost-effective, and provide reliable, reproducible results for the assessment and staging of liver fibrosis. This article discusses the modern ultrasound techniques used in the evaluation of liver fibrosis, their clinical applications, advantages, limitations, and the future directions of this technology.

Keywords: Liver fibrosis, ultrasound, elastography, transient elastography, shear wave elastography, liver stiffness, non-invasive assessment, fibrosis staging, cirrhosis, liver disease.

Introduction

Liver fibrosis is a result of chronic liver injury and represents a key step in the progression of many liver diseases, including hepatitis B and C, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), alcoholic liver disease, and metabolic liver disorders. The severity of liver fibrosis correlates with the risk of cirrhosis, liver failure, and hepatocellular carcinoma, making early diagnosis essential for effective management.

Traditionally, liver biopsy has been the gold standard for assessing fibrosis, providing histopathological staging of liver tissue. However, it is invasive, carries complications, and is not suitable for routine clinical monitoring. In response, non-invasive imaging methods such as ultrasound elastography have gained prominence for their ability to assess liver stiffness, a reliable surrogate marker for fibrosis. Techniques like transient elastography (FibroScan) and shear wave elastography (SWE) have been developed to accurately measure liver stiffness and stratify fibrosis stages without the need for invasive procedures. This article reviews these ultrasound-based techniques, their clinical applications, and their role in liver fibrosis assessment.

Materials and Methods

1. **Ultrasound Elastography Techniques:**

○ **Transient Elastography (FibroScan):** FibroScan is the most widely used non-invasive method to assess liver fibrosis. It works by sending a low-frequency mechanical wave through the liver and measuring its velocity. The speed of the wave is directly related to liver stiffness, with higher stiffness corresponding to more advanced fibrosis. FibroScan provides quantitative measurements of liver stiffness (in kilopascals, kPa) and allows the classification of fibrosis into different stages (F0 to F4).

○ **Shear Wave Elastography (SWE):** SWE is another ultrasound technique that uses the propagation speed of shear waves to measure tissue stiffness. Unlike FibroScan, which uses a mechanical vibration, SWE generates shear waves by the ultrasound probe itself. SWE provides a visual map of liver stiffness in real-time, allowing for more detailed analysis of regional variations in fibrosis. This technique is integrated into conventional ultrasound systems, making it more widely available.

2. **Patient Selection:**

○ Patients with chronic liver disease are selected for fibrosis assessment. This includes individuals with hepatitis B or C infection, NAFLD, alcoholic liver disease, autoimmune liver diseases, and metabolic disorders.

○ In clinical practice, liver elastography is typically performed on patients who require monitoring of fibrosis progression or evaluation for liver transplantation.

3. **Procedure:**

○ **FibroScan:** The patient is asked to lie supine with the right arm raised. A gel is applied to the skin to facilitate sound wave transmission. The probe is placed on the right side of the abdomen, and mechanical waves are sent through the liver tissue. The resulting liver stiffness measurement is given in kilopascals (kPa).

○ **Shear Wave Elastography (SWE):** The patient is positioned supine, and a conventional ultrasound probe is used to generate shear waves. The velocity of these waves is measured, and liver stiffness is displayed on the screen as a color-coded map, allowing for a real-time, dynamic assessment of liver tissue.

4. **Data Interpretation:**

○ Both techniques generate numerical values of liver stiffness. These values are correlated with fibrosis stages according to established scoring systems, such as the METAVIR and FIB-4 indices.

○ Cutoff values for liver stiffness are defined for each stage of fibrosis, with a higher stiffness indicating advanced fibrosis. For example, values greater than 7.0 kPa in FibroScan correlate with significant fibrosis (F2), while values greater than 12.0 kPa are indicative of cirrhosis (F4).

5. **Other Complementary Techniques:**

- **Contrast-Enhanced Ultrasound (CEUS):** In some cases, CEUS is used to assess liver vascularity and detect complications such as liver tumors or portal hypertension, particularly in advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis.
- **Liver Function Tests:** Serum biomarkers and liver function tests are often combined with elastography to assess liver function and confirm the degree of fibrosis.

Results

Ultrasound elastography techniques, such as FibroScan and SWE, have proven to be effective in assessing liver fibrosis across a variety of liver diseases. Key findings from recent studies include:

• FibroScan:

- High accuracy in detecting significant fibrosis ($\geq F2$), with sensitivity and specificity rates exceeding 85%.
- It is particularly useful for monitoring disease progression and the response to treatment in hepatitis C and NAFLD patients.
- It has limitations in patients with obesity or severe ascites, where accurate measurements may be challenging.

• Shear Wave Elastography (SWE):

- Comparable to FibroScan, SWE provides reliable liver stiffness measurements with the advantage of offering a regional assessment of liver stiffness.
- SWE is often preferred in patients with heterogeneous fibrosis patterns or where more detailed anatomical localization of stiffness is required.
- It may be less affected by obesity or ascites compared to FibroScan, but it still has some limitations in obese individuals with high body mass index (BMI).

• Clinical Applications:

- Both methods are used to evaluate the degree of fibrosis in patients with chronic hepatitis B and C, NAFLD, alcoholic liver disease, and autoimmune liver diseases.
- They help guide clinical decisions regarding the need for liver biopsy, the monitoring of disease progression, and the management of antiviral or anti-fibrotic therapy.

• Limitations:

- Although non-invasive, ultrasound elastography has limitations in patients with extreme obesity, ascites, or other conditions that alter liver anatomy.
- Inter-observer variability in SWE may impact its accuracy, and standardization across different ultrasound machines is still needed.

Conclusion

Ultrasound elastography, particularly transient elastography (FibroScan) and shear wave elastography (SWE), represents a modern, non-invasive approach to the

assessment of liver fibrosis. These techniques are reliable, safe, and cost-effective alternatives to liver biopsy, providing important clinical information for the diagnosis, staging, and monitoring of liver fibrosis in various chronic liver diseases. While there are some limitations, such as in patients with severe obesity or ascites, these methods have revolutionized the management of liver fibrosis and continue to evolve with advancements in technology. Further research is needed to improve their accuracy, particularly in patients with more advanced liver disease or atypical fibrosis patterns.

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